

A Shannon Tsallis Hybrid?

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In previous notes, we have argued that in the Shannon case, the probability associated with a conserved quantity e_i is $f(e_i)$, while for the Tsallis case it is $f(e_i)$ power q , leading to the constraints $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)$ and $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)$ power q in entropy extremization. We argued that $f(e_i)$ power q could arise physically in the case of the germination of a sunflower seed. If $f(e_i)$ is the probability that the seed is not eaten in a day and germination takes q days then $f(e_i)$ power q is the probability for germination if the only hindrance to the process is the seed being eaten by a bird. Here we consider mixed sunflower seeds. A fraction "a" germinates in 1 day while the fraction b, in 2 days, where $a+b=1$. We use the notion of extremization of entropy to find the distribution $f(e_i)$ which is linked to a decaying exponential, but damped by the factor a as well as $F(f)$ where $F=\ln$ in the Shannon case and $\ln q$ in the Tsallis. We consider the limiting cases of $a \rightarrow 1$, $b \rightarrow 0$ and $a \rightarrow \delta$, $b \rightarrow 1-\delta$, where δ is tiny as well.

Extremization of Entropy Approach

We argued in previous notes that extremization of entropy hinges on the constraints one uses. We consider the physical problem of germination of two kinds of sunflower seeds mixed together in proportional a and b such that:

$$a+b=1 \quad ((1))$$

$f(e_i)$ is the probability that a seed is not eaten by a bird in a day regardless of whether it is type a or b and depends on e_i , the amount of fruit produced by a seed if it is grown in region i. The key condition is that type a seeds take 1 day to germinate, while type b, 2 days. Thus, on average, the probability to germinate is:

$$a f(e_i) + b f(e_i) f(e_i) \quad ((2))$$

"a" seeds are linked with Shannon entropy and "b" seeds with Tsallis $q=2$. The production e_i is the same for type a and b seeds if they germinate. Thus, one has a hybrid Shannon/Tsallis situation, we argue.

The entropy approach is to write:

Probability linked with e_i production * $F(f(e_i))$ such that:

$$F(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad \text{and} \quad \text{probability linked with } e_i \text{ production } d/d f \quad F(f) = \text{constant} \quad ((3))$$

For the Shannon case, $F=\ln$ and for the Tsallis, $F= (f(e_i) \text{ power } (1-q) - 1) / (1-q)$ ((4))
The probability linked with e_i production is ((2)). Thus,

$$dF/df = 1 / \{ f (a+bf) \} \text{ for } a>0 \quad ((5))$$

We use partial fraction to deal with ((5)), but this approach only works if $a>0$. One may, however, use then $b=0$, $a=1$ and obtain the Shannon result, but cannot use $a=0$, $b=1$ to obtain the Tsallis $q=2$ result. One can, however, set $a=\delta$, $b=1-\delta$, $\delta \ll 1$ to recover Tsallis $q=2$ results as we show.

$$dF/f = 1/ (ax) -b/ \{a (a+bx)\} \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{Integrating over } df \text{ yields: } F(f) = \ln(f)/a - \ln(a+bf) /a + \text{constant} \quad ((7))$$

For $a=1$, $b=0$, and $\text{constant}=0$, one obtains Shannon information $\ln(f)$. One cannot officially use $b=1$, $a=0$ because the approach of partial fractions breaks down in such a case. One can, however, use $a=\delta$ and $b=1-\delta$. In such a case:

$$F(f) = \ln(f)/\delta - 1/\delta \{ \ln((1-\delta) f) + \delta/((1-\delta)f) \} + \text{constant}$$

$$\text{Next set } 1-\delta \text{ approx } 1 \text{ and one has: } F(f) = -1/f + \text{constant} \quad ((8))$$

The Tsallis $\ln_q(f)$ for $q=2$ is: $1-1/f$ and so this result is recovered for $\text{constant} = 1$.

Now to find $f(e_i)$, one may note that:

$$-e_i/T = F(f) \text{ or } f(e_i/T) / \{a + b f(e_i)\} = \exp (-a(e_i/T-\text{constant})) \text{ or:}$$

$$f(e_i) = C \exp(-a (e_i/T-\text{constant})) / \{1- b \exp (-a (e_i/T-\text{constant})) \} \quad ((9))$$

where C is a normalization constant.

For $a=1$, $b=0$, one obtains $\exp(-e_i/T)$, the Shannon result. One cannot use $a=0$, $b=1$ in this procedure. One may, however, see that the presence of $0 < a < 1$ slows down the exponential drop of the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution associated with Shannon's entropy. The smaller the portion of a , the slower the drop in the exponential.

If one considers $a=\delta$ and $b=1-\delta$ in ((9)) with $\text{constant} = 1$, then with $C=1$:

$$f(e_i) = \{1- \delta(1-e/T)\} / \{\delta (1-e/T)\} \text{ with the dominant term proportional to } 1/(1-e/T) \quad ((10))$$

The Tsallis $\exp_q(x) = (1+ (1-q) x)$ power $1/(1-q)$ so for $q=2$ and $x=e_i/T$ one has:

$$(1-e_i/T) \text{ power } -1 \quad ((11))$$

Thus, the Tsallis result is obtained in the limit $a \rightarrow \delta$, $b \rightarrow 1-\delta$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that it is possible to have a Shannon-Tsallis hybrid. We consider the probability which should appear with e_i as: $a f(e_i) + b f(e_i)f(e_i)$, where $a+b=1$. For $a=1, b=0$, one has Shannon's case, while for $b=1, a=0$, Tsallis $q=2$. The approach of partial fractions that we use does not allow for $a=0$, but we can use $a=\delta \ll 1$ to obtain the Tsallis result. We use the extremization of entropy argument that there exists an $F(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ such that : probability for e_i * $dF/df = \text{constant}$. We argue that $af+bf$ is the probability which applies to the germination of a mixture of two types of sunflower seeds, a and b . " a " takes one day to germinate and b , two days. A seed germinates if it is not eaten by a bird, and $f(e_i)$ is the probability for it not to be eaten in a day.

We find that $F(f) = \ln(f)/a - \ln(a+bf) /a + \text{constant}$. We show that for $a=\delta, b=1-\delta, \delta \ll 1$ one retrieves $\ln q$ for $q=2$ for $\text{constant}=2$. We show that the general solution for f is: $C \exp(-a (e_i/T-\text{constant})) / \{1- b \exp (-a (e_i/T-\text{constant})) \}$ and show that this yields the Shannon result for $a=1, b=0$ and the Tsallis $q=2$ result for $a=\delta, b=1-\delta$.